

OBJECTIVE SIGNIFICANCE OF CYBER CRIMES

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Abstract This article discusses the negligible risk of prosecution, suggesting that cybercrime is global and has no geopolitical boundaries. This means that it is more difficult to find a cybercriminal, and international investigations and cooperation require significant financial resources.

Keywords: cybercrime, IT technology, computer and Internet, information and technology, hacker

When talking about cybercrime, they should understand that this phenomenon is a consequence of the global spread of IT technologies, but if we compare cybercrime with other types of criminal activity, then cybercrime is growing at a much faster pace. It depends on the following factors [1]:

- 1 Constant growth in the number of computer and Internet users.
- 2 Constantly increasing the level of professionalism of criminals in cyberspace.
- 3 Improvement and development of IT technologies.

Everything related to the development of IT technologies is the basis for committing cybercrimes[2].

The development and improvement of information and technical tools is not the only thing that affects the change and development of cybercrime.

Talking about the negligible risk of prosecution means that cybercrime is global and has no geopolitical boundaries, which means that it is more difficult for authorities to find a cybercriminal, and international investigation and cooperation require large financial resources. The increasing public loyalty to cybercriminals is due to the fact that cybercriminals are often considered by the cybercriminal

community for free speech, free software, and Internet goods, so business owners often conduct clandestine businesses over the Internet, as well as think about providing it. Protection through cyber structures, in this case, the threat to government structures, is already considered. Finally, the third reason for the development of cybercrime as a clandestine business refers to the ease of committing cybercrimes: on the Internet, you can find many materials, algorithms and explanations for committing cybercrimes [3].

In the field of cybercrime, the group of criminals with high knowledge is considered the most dangerous and can have the following qualities [4]:

1 Cybercrime activities are often under the jurisdiction of different countries and cross-border.

2 A cybercriminal has the ability to combine cybercrime tools (eg computers) into a single mechanism in an automated manner.

3 The criminal has personal qualities such as high professional and intellectual data.

4 Cybercrimes can be committed anonymously.

5 Lack of information about the crime committed by the victim of cybercrime or receiving this information with a delay in time.

6 The perpetrator does not have to have direct contact with the victim of cybercrime.

Thus, the high risk of cybercrime is explained, first of all, by the growing role of the system of social relations that it threatens, its global and organized nature, and the presence of hackers and cybercriminals with a high level of knowledge in the field of cybercrime.

In conclusion, it can be said that cybercrime has already passed the formative stage and has reached a new stage, and it is developing day by day.

The hacker himself has also changed: from an amateur to a professional who is part of the criminal business. Cybercriminals also cause great harm to individual

citizens, organizations, enterprises, and the entire national economy, and pose a minimal threat to themselves.

The main factors affecting the occurrence of economic cybercrimes are:

- economic crisis;
- increase in the price of basic goods;
- decrease in standard of living;
- increase in the unemployment rate.

The main sources of crimes committed in cyberspace are:

- illegal business activity;
- illegal banking activity;
- organization and conduct of gambling games.

Besides being a platform for illegal activities, the Internet is also a place for laundering proceeds of crime. The World Wide Web and the cyberspace created by it created a unique environment and unique conditions for implementing criminal activities (legalization of proceeds of crime, quick and stable income). The laundering of criminal proceeds in cyberspace creates difficulties in the practice of law enforcement, which leads to the need to improve legislation.

The set of methods of legalization of funds received because of committing cybercrime includes: the use of social networks, auction sites, and advertising sites, besides these tools, the attacker can open and use various types of his own sites. existing internet banks and Bitcoin cryptocurrency.

Thus, to legalize money, familiar operations are used that any person can perform.

One of the most common ways to withdraw money is to sell non-existent properties through advertising sites. The criminal creates several accounts on the site, registers under different names from different addresses, and displays different products on the site, most importantly, without the real existence of the goods. Then, as a buyer, he uses the proceeds of crime.

First, the offender transfers money in electronic currency to pre-arranged fake electronic money system accounts.

Second, he transfers money from these accounts to the e-wallets of supposedly different buyers. Third, the attacker buys non-existent goods that he himself has put up for sale as a seller on behalf of each "fake buyer". The money received as a result of this scheme will be transferred to the applicable bank account. To confirm the legality of the income received, an extract from the purchase history of the site or other documents indicating the legal nature of the income can be provided.

With the emergence of new technologies, new, more complex types of crime are emerging. This indicates that criminals quickly use the results of scientific and technical development for their own purposes. This trend seriously threatens all social relations that develop in cyberspace, because at this stage of development, cyberspace and society are already inseparable.

The main reasons and conditions for the existence of economic cybercrime are the anonymity of users of cyberspace and the anonymity of information networks, technical shortcomings, as well as the low level of information security of people. Only a small fraction of economic cybercrimes are reported to law enforcement.

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